

COMPARISON OF PRESUMPTIVE DIAGNOSIS AND LABORATORY DIAGNOSIS IN
(SUSPECTED) CASES OF NEONATAL MENINGITIS

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ABSTRACT

The very nature of day-to-day medical practice often requires that clinicians engage their clinical judgment to reach a presumptive diagnosis while awaiting evidence-based laboratory diagnosis. Sometimes however- particularly in medical emergencies- clinical actions have to be taken on the strength of tentative presumptive diagnosis. This implies that though the laboratory diagnosis would still invariably correct the clinician's clinical judgment-if it was erroneous- it is still in the patient's best interest for the clinician's tentative presumptive diagnosis to be as near-accurate as any other visually-guided human judgment can be. This study compared the presumptive diagnosis of (suspected) cases of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis with subsequent laboratory diagnosis. Forty-five (suspected) cases of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis between October, 2011 and September, 2013 at a tertiary health facility in Ekiti State (South-West) Nigeria were retrospectively analysed. The inclusion criteria were; patients aged 0-31 days and who had their CSF samples collected for m/c/s on the suspicion of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis or other related neonatal diseases. 48.9% of the subjects were males while 51.1% were females. 30(66.7%) were aged 0-7days; 8(17.8%) 8-15 days; 6(13.3%) 16-23days and 1(2.2%) 1day. 36(80%) of the neonates were admitted at the Hospital's SCBU; 3(6.7%) at the CEW while 6(13.3%) were attended to at the COPD. 60% were presumptively diagnosed of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis, 39% of neonatal sepsis and 1% of jaundice. However, the results show that laboratory-confirmed neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis was 0(0%). This shows a statistically significant difference between presumptive and laboratory diagnosis of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis. The study examines the implications of the wide disparity between the clinicians' presumptive diagnosis of neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis and the laboratory's diagnosis

KEYWORDS: neonatal cerebrospinal meningitis, presumptive diagnosis, laboratory diagnosis, clinical impression, clinical judgment.

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INTRODUCTION

Meningitis- the inflammation of the meninges- is one of the leading causes of neonatal morbidity and mortality, especially in developing countries (Obaro, 2011; Stevens *et al*, 2003; Chang *et al*, 2004; de Louvois *et al*, 2004) and Nigeria is said to be responsible for 8.3% of all global neonatal deaths (Olusanya *et al*, 2012). It has been established that newly-born babies and those living in poverty-ravaged countries are particularly susceptible to cerebrospinal meningitis- though there are other predisposing factors such as geographical location etc (Kwang, 2010; Kim, 2003). Also, severity of sickness on presentation at the hospital, inadequate knowledge of the pathogenesis of cerebrospinal meningitis and multi-drug resistance, have equally been fingered as additional factors that contribute to high mortality of meningitis(Appelbaum, 1992; Akanbi, 2004; Akpede,1994). In untreated cases, the mortality of meningitis inches towards 100% and this evidently and unarguably makes

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cerebrospinal meningitis a medical emergency, anywhere, anytime. (Doran et al, 2005; Rubin and Staddon, 1999).

Though any human pathogen is a potential aetiological of meningitis, a narrow spectrum of organisms causes majority of all cases of cerebrospinal meningitis. Within this narrow spectrum are; *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Niesseria meningidits*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Haemophilus influenzae* (Kwang, 2010). Of all meningitis-causing organisms, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* are responsible for most of the mortality attributed to cerebrospinal meningitis. In Nigeria for example, *S pneumoniae* kills about 200,000 under-five kids(Onoche, 2009; Falade, 2009). It is said also to be responsible for 13% of all deaths in North Central Nigeria and 80% of meningitis-related under-five deaths in South-West Nigeria(Obaro, 2011; Falade, 2009)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study is a retrospective case-analyses of forty-five neonates aged 0-31 days attended to or hospitalised at a tertiary health facility in Ado-Ekiti (Southwest) Nigeria, between October 2011 and September, 2013. The subjects comprised twenty-two males and twenty-three females. Data about the subjects were obtained through their clinical and personal details supplied by the clinicians who ordered for csf m/c/s for the subjects.

Table 1: Sex Distribution

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	22	48.9
Female	23	51.1
Total	45	100

The patients were admitted/attended to at the Special Care Baby Unit (SCBU), Children Out-Patient Department and Children Emergency Ward of the Hospital.

Table 2: Ward Distribution

Ward	Frequency	Percentage
*SCBU	36	80
**COPD	6	13.3
***CEW	3	6.7
Total	45	100

Table 3: Age Distribution

Age Bracket(Days)	Frequency	Percentage
0-7	30	66.7
8-15	8	17.8
16-23	6	13.3
24-31	1	2.2
Total	45	100

*Special Care Baby Unit **Children Out-Patient Department ***Children Emergency Ward

The subjects were presumptively diagnosed of cerebrospinal meningitis, neonatal sepsis or jaundice and had their CSF samples collected and sent to the laboratory for appropriate investigation. Each CSF sample was plated on chocolate and Macconkey agar and incubated at 37°C. The total white blood cells count of the samples

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were also determined and stained using the Gram staining technique. The incubated plates were 'read' the following morning after overnight incubation at 37°C.

RESULT

Apart from the samples which were visibly blood-stained and therefore unsuitable for total WBC assay, all the CSF samples contained $< 5 \times 10^6/L$ of white blood cells. Microscopic examination of the Gram-stained smears of the samples showed that none of the samples contained any detectable bacterial cells. Incidence of presumptive neonatal meningitis was 60%, while the incidence of evidence-based (ie Laboratory-confirmed) meningitis was 0% (Table 4).

Table 4: Incidence of neonatal meningitis

Disease	Presumptive Diagnosis	Lab-confirmed Diagnosis
Neonatal meningitis	60%	0%
Neonatal sepsis	39%	NI*
Jaundice	1%	NI*

* Not Investigated

DISCUSSION

Scientific-evidence and basis are the hallmarks of modern medicine (Silva *et al*, 2013), without which western medicine would be mere guess-medicine as was the case century ago. Laboratory diagnosis has therefore become the traditional gold standard for diagnosis in Medicine. A clinician could confirm the veracity and accuracy or otherwise of his clinical impression, which form the basis of his tentative presumptive diagnosis. However, like any other non-evidence-based cases of human judgment, the tentative presumptive diagnosis may be inaccurate (Rekha and Jyothi, 2010) and this can lead to case mismanagement. This is expected naturally, because any treatment plan designed on the basis of a false and inaccurate diagnosis will surely lead to treatment failure (Malhotra *et al*, 2003).

This study found a statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between the clinicians' tentative presumptive diagnosis of cerebrospinal meningitis (60%) and laboratory diagnosis of cerebrospinal meningitis (0%) in the 45 neonates included in this study. This is quite in tandem with the findings of Rekha and Jyothi(2010). In their study, they investigated the accuracies or otherwise of visual presumptive diagnosis of symptomatic vaginal discharge among 203 women of reproductive age attended to at a Bangalore (India) tertiary hospital vis-à-vis the laboratory diagnosis of vaginal discharge cases. They compared the presumptive diagnosis of bacterial vaginosis, candidiasis and trichomoniasis reached by clinicians with the microbiological diagnosis made by the laboratory. Their results show that 71%, 24% and 13% bacterial vaginosis, candidiasis and trichomoniasis presumptive diagnosis were made respectively whereas only 33%, 16% and 13% lab-confirmed microbiological diagnosis were made.

Though the present study doesn't in anyway question or query the clinical judgment of the clinicians involved in the management of the subjects, but it raises two vital issues. First, in the absence of appropriate microbiological investigation of cerebrospinal meningitis- especially as it obtains in resource-limited rural settings, where even basic microbiological facilities are non-existent- the patients would have been wrongly treated (on the strength of false presumptive diagnosis) for diseases that didn't ail them. Similar observation was made by Rekha and Jyothi(2010). They noted that if blanket therapy were given to the women with vaginal discharge who participated in their study (on the strength of presumptive diagnosis and syndromic management alone) 44% and 81% of the women would have received antibiotic and anti-fungal treatments unnecessarily.

If syndromic treatment dictated only by presumptive diagnosis had been blanketly given to the subjects in this present study, a shocking 100% of the subjects would have received antibiotic treatment for a disease they never

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suffered from, with its attendant implications, such as drug-resistance development, treatment failure, treatment-cost inefficiency among others.

Second, this study further re-echoes the need for thorough and comprehensive laboratory investigation for every suspected disease. The importance of this in modern-day Medicine cannot be over-emphasised

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